

ISic3161

I.Sicily inscription 3161

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI329771

1. [— — — —] καλανδῶν Ἰου-
2. [— — — ἐ]τελεύτα Φηλη-
3. [κί]ων κὲ ²⁷Φηλη|[— ἐτ]ῶν κε(?) (Tod)²⁷ ἐνθά-
4. [δε καθ]ίζε [ται(?) — —]
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645491

PHI 329771

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 16.0536

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 116 ph

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